

LOW VELOCITY IMPACT DAMAGE OF CARBON/PEEK
CROSSPLY LAMINATES

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ABSTRACT

This work deals with damage growth in Carbon/PEEK crossply laminates under low velocity impact. Both experimental and numerical investigations were conducted. It is found that the thermal residual stresses have significant effects on transverse matrix cracks. The Mode II dominated delaminations seem to be arrested at a constant interlaminar fracture energy value. The strain energy release rate at delamination arrest is estimated and seems to be close to the Mode II initiation value under static loading.

KEYWORDS: Thermoplastic Composite; Low Velocity Impact; Delamination Arrest; Strain Energy Release Rate; Residual Stress.

1. INTRODUCTION

Resistance to impact damage is of critical importance in the application of composite materials to aircraft structures [1, 2]. A large number of research works have been devoted to the study of impact damage, mostly in epoxy-based composites [1-5].

In recent years, high performance thermoplastic composites have been favorably considered for structural applications because these thermoplastic materials exhibit higher toughness than the thermosets. Consequently the matrix-controlled failure modes such as transverse matrix crack and delamination induced by impact should be reduced. The impact damage behavior of thermoplastic laminated composites has been studied in [6-11] and needs to be further understood. The present work is a continuation of the previous study [11] on the low velocity impact damage of

Carbon/PEEK laminates. The damage growth behavior and the effects of thermal residual stresses are considered.

2. EXPERIMENT

Square plates 152.4 by 152.4 mm were fabricated from the Carbon/PEEK thermoplastic composite APC-2, following the recommended molding cycle [12]. Three crossply layups were selected: $[0_5, 90_5, 0_5]$ (Laminates A), $[0_3, 90_3, 0_3, 90_3, 0_3]$ (Laminates B) and $[0, 90, \dots, 90, 0]_{15t}$ (Laminates C). These laminate types have been studied in [4] for impact damage mechanisms of epoxy composites, and in [9] for the thermoplastic polyphenylene sulfide (PPS) composite.

The impact tests were conducted on a Dynatup-8200 impact tester. The plate was fixed around its four edges, leaving a test section of 128 x 128 mm. The impactor, 1.27 kg in mass, had a steel hemispherical nose of 12.7 mm in diameter. The impact energy varied between 1 and 20 J. After impact, the specimen was inspected by X-radiography and then unstacked by the thermal depley technique. Details of the test procedure can be found in [11].

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Fig. 1 shows the impact force history of an A Laminate subjected to 5 J impact. A small-amplitude signal with higher frequencies was found superimposed on the basic load-time curve. This signal seems to be related to the damage growth during impact [6]. It ceased when unloading began, possibly implying the arrest of major

Figure 1. Impact force history of a three-layer crossply laminate under 5 J impact.

damage growth at about the time of maximum impact load. The loading duration t_1 and the unloading duration t_2 can be identified by 5-order polynomial smoothing of the load-time curve.

Fig. 2 shows the typical damage patterns of laminates A and B respectively. The same damage mechanisms as in epoxy composites were observed. For both laminate types, below 10 J impact, transverse matrix cracking and delamination were the major damage modes and no fiber breakage was found. At 10 J impact and above, local indentation crash occurred in both laminates. In Laminate C, fewer matrix cracks and less delamination were observed. Fiber breakage and penetration are the major damage modes in this laminate.

Figure 2. Low velocity impact damage in Carbon/PEEK crossply laminates:
(a) Laminate A, 5 J; (b) Laminate B, 10 J.

Figure 3. Total delamination area versus impact energy for Carbon/PEEK laminates.

Evenly distributed matrix crack patterns were observed in both Laminates A and B in the 90-degree layer(s). These cracks extended across the whole span of the plate in Laminate A, but were distributed within an apparently elliptical region in Laminate B. For both Laminates, a group of short 90-degree cracks were distributed around the major delamination in the laminate and seemed to be associated with the delamination growth.

In Fig. 3, the total delamination area, as measured from the delamination image in the X-ray picture, is plotted against impact energy. Linear relationships are observed in both laminates A and B. As expected, the slope of the plot for Laminate B is lower than that for Laminate A, confirming the effect of ply thickness on delamination sizes as commonly observed [4]. No penetration occurred for Laminate A and the damage area extended up to the clamped edges at 10 J impact. Penetration occurred in Laminate B at 15 J. In Laminate C, little delamination was observed and complete penetration occurred at about 13 J impact for this laminate.

As commonly observed in epoxy-based crossply laminates, the impact delamination at an interface is also of a 'peanut shape' in these Carbon/PEEK composite laminates. The delamination geometry can be characterized by defining its length (L) and width (W) along the fiber direction of the lower ply and in the corresponding transverse direction, respectively [11]. Figs. 4(a) and 4(b) show the delamination sizes versus impact energy for both Laminates A and B respectively. The major delamination occurred at the 2nd interface of Laminate A and the 4th interface of Laminate B, it formed a narrow strip along the 0-degree fiber direction.

Figure 4. Sizes of delaminations versus incident impact energy:
(a) Laminate A; (b) Laminate B.

The impact damage discussed above involves a complex dynamic fracture process, which seems to be inaccessible by the available analysis procedures. As a first attempt for understanding, the stress response in the intact laminate was considered. This stress field consists of two parts : the local contact stresses which control the damage initiation, and the plate bending stresses which act in the area of damage growth. For the purposes of this study, the plate bending stress field was considered and was evaluated by the shear deformable laminate theory. The problem was simulated as a square plate being impacted at its center by a concentrated force. The measured impact force history was applied. Transient dynamic finite element analyses were performed using the structural analysis program ABAQUS, with the details being described in [11].

As discussed in [5], the three dimensional matrix failure criterion (tensile mode) [13] was employed to define the strength ratio of transverse matrix failure, R_m in each layer, i.e.

$$R_m = \frac{\sigma_{22}^2}{\sigma_T^2} + \frac{\tau_{23}^2}{\tau_T^2} + \frac{(\tau_{12}^2 + \tau_{13}^2)}{\tau_{LT}^2} \quad (1)$$

where σ_{22} , σ_{12} , σ_{13} , σ_{23} are the stress components, σ_T , τ_T , and τ_{LT} are the material strengths, all defined in the material symmetry axes with 1 being the fiber direction (L), 2 and 3 being the in-plane and out-of-plane transverse directions(T) respectively. Failure occurs when $R_m = 1.0$. The transverse normal stress, σ_{33} , is omitted in Eq. 1 because it rapidly drops to zero away from the contact zone [3].

What controls the delamination growth is not known at present. A clue to this problem has been found when a close association between the interlaminar shear stress and the delamination growth was observed in [11]. The dynamic interlaminar shear stresses were evaluated by integrating the following local equilibrium equations from layer to layer:

$$\tau_{xz,z} = -(\sigma_{x,x} + \tau_{xy,y}) \quad (2)$$

$$\tau_{yz,z} = -(\sigma_{y,y} + \tau_{xy,x}) \quad (3)$$

where σ_x , σ_y , τ_{xy} , τ_{xz} and τ_{yz} are the stress components in Cartesian coordinates, with x and y along the 0 and 90 degree fiber directions respectively. Since Eqs. 2 and 3 represent the in-plane equilibrium of a material point which undergoes negligible in-plane movement, both gravity and inertia forces have been dropped.

The material constants used in the analysis were taken from the ICI documentation [14] because the material property test in [12] gave similar values. The thermal residual strains in the transverse direction of both 0 and 90-degree layers were estimated by the 'First-Ply-Failure' method and the laminate theory [15]. In the transverse direction of both 0 and 90-degree layers, the estimated residual strains were found to be 0.644% and 0.707% respectively in Laminate A, and 0.573% and 0.604% respectively in Laminate B. In Laminate C, no 'First-Ply-Failure' was observed and the effect of residual stresses were not considered for this laminate.

Figure 5. Comparison between the predicted and observed transverse matrix failure regions.
 (a) Laminate A, 2nd layer, 5 J; (b) Laminate B, 4th layer, 10 J.

Figure 6. Interlaminar shear stress contours at the instant of maximum impact load.

Figures 5(a) and 5(b) show respectively the strength ratios of transverse matrix failure in the 90-degree layer of Laminate A subjected to a 5 J impact, and Laminate B subjected to a 10 J impact. The results suggest that the predictions with consideration of residual thermal stresses agree well with the test observations,

except for the cross-span extension of the matrix cracks in Laminate A. This discrepancy is probably due to the fact that the matrix cracks in a thicker layer are less constrained by neighboring layers, and their growth is more controlled by the fracture process at the crack tips. When the ply thickness is smaller (Laminate B), the predicted failure area agrees with the elliptical distribution of 90-degree cracks. The results also show that predictions without considering the residual stresses greatly underestimate the extent of matrix failure.

Fig. 6 shows the contour plots of interlaminar shear stresses, τ_{xz} and τ_{yz} , at the instant of maximum impact load, for different interfaces of laminates A and B. It is observed that, at the 2nd interface of Laminate A and the 4th interface of Laminate B, the high-value contours of τ_{xz} occur within a narrow strip along the x-axis, and these stress contours exhibit 'peanut-shapes' which resemble the observed delaminations at these interfaces. The other stress component, τ_{yz} , is very low. These observations suggest that the delamination growth at these interfaces occurred in a τ_{xz} dominated area and thus in a Mode II dominated fracture process. This is in agreement with the fractographic analysis of the delamination surfaces [11]. It is worth noting that the previous work [16] has shown that, in the flexural beam, when the crack is not located at mid-plane, delamination does not occur in a pure Mode II but Mode I is also present. Consequently, although the above results suggest that Mode II is dominant in the delamination process, the interlaminar crack growth could possibly be controlled by a mixed-mode of fracture. Similar analyses for Laminate C show that the transverse matrix failure is suppressed near the mid plane, where the interlaminar shear stresses are high. Matrix failure occurs in the layers near the non-impacted surface, but the interlaminar shear stresses at the adjacent interfaces are very low. This mismatch of initiation mechanism and the crack growth driving force explains the lower degree of delamination in Laminates C. In another respect, fiber failure occurs early in this laminate.

Figure 7. Nominal interlaminar shear stress at delamination arrest.

Figure 8. Unloading compliance C versus 2nd delamination length L_2 for Laminate A.

Assuming the major delamination growth to be arrested at the time of maximum impact load, the correlation between the measured delamination sizes in Fig. 4 and the stress contours in Fig. 6 gives the nominal stress level at which delamination arrest occurs. Such nominal stresses are shown in Fig. 7 for the major delaminations in both Laminates A and B, respectively. At the arrested front of these Mode II dominated delaminations, the controlling nominal stress τ_{xz} varies between 11.63 and 18.62 MPa, and is less affected by the layer thickness. Similar correlations for the 2nd and 3rd interfaces of Laminate B gave higher stress values. This may be due to a different contribution from Mode I and Mode III modes at these interfaces and/or the less contribution from the transverse matrix cracks.

The results in Fig. 7 again confirm the uniqueness of the nominal shear stress, τ_{xz} , at the arrested delamination front for the plate geometry considered. This observation has been explained, in the previous work [11], in terms of a possible constant stress intensity factor in the sample. In order to verify this assumption, the global strain energy release rates in Laminate A are considered. The quasi-static strain energy release rate, G , can be expressed in terms of the specimen compliance, C , i.e.

$$G = \frac{P^2}{2} \frac{dC}{dA} \quad (4)$$

where A is the crack surface area and P is the load. From the recorded impact load-time history in Fig. 1, the specimen compliance can be evaluated by the spring-mass model:

$$t = \pi M^{\frac{1}{2}} (C + C_m)^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (5)$$

where t is the impact duration, M is the mass of the impactor, C is the specimen compliance, and C_m is the system compliance which is neglected in this study. From the unloading duration, t_2 , in the recorded impact load-time history, the compliance of the specimen containing a delamination can be evaluated. As discussed in [11], the delamination width, W_2 , seems to be controlled by the initiation process and increases only slightly with impact energy (Fig. 4(a)). Crack arrest occurs at the delamination front which defines the delamination length L_2 . Thus, with \overline{W}_2 being the average width, the following growth pattern is assumed:

$$dA = \overline{W}_2 dL_2 \quad (6)$$

Fig. 8 shows the unloading compliance C versus the delamination length L_2 . The result suggests that, within the scatter of the data, C can be considered to vary linearly with the delamination length L_2 .

As discussed earlier, the observed impact damage process seems to cease around the maximum load. From Eq. 4, if the maximum load is considered to be associated with the crack arrest process, the strain energy release rate at crack arrest, G_{arr} , can be calculated. Fig. 9 plots the maximum impact load versus L_2 . It is clear that, with the above assumption, G_{arr} cannot be considered as a material constant to characterize the impact induced delamination in laminated composites.

Figure 9. Maximum impact load versus 2nd delamination length L_2 for Laminate A.

Figure 10. (Δ_{arr}/C) as a function of 2nd delamination length L_2 for Laminate A.

In the previous work [11], it has been found that the delamination in these laminates would result from an unstable crack growth. The previous investigations on impact fracture of polymers and composites [17-19] have also shown that unstable fracture occurs under a displacement controlled condition [17, 18]. The crack velocity in an unstable propagation is much higher than the impact speed [17, 19] and the energy required to make this propagation is supplied by the elastic energy stored in the sample. Under a displacement controlled condition, the strain energy release rate at crack arrest, G_{arr} , can be expressed by:

$$G_{arr} = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\Delta_{arr}}{C} \right)^2 \frac{dC}{dA} \quad (7)$$

where Δ_{arr} is the central deflection at delamination arrest, which, in this case, is assumed to be the deflection at maximum impact load. Fig. 10 shows (Δ_{arr}/C) as a function of L_2 . The results seem to demonstrate the existence of a constant delamination arrest toughness, G_{arr} , and confirm again that the unstable crack propagation occurs under a displacement controlled condition. From the limited test data in the study, this value is estimated to be between 1.23 and 2.77 kJ/m² with an average of 1.69 kJ/m², which is close to the Mode II initiation toughness of 1.81 kJ/m² of this material [20]. It must be noted that the initiation value in [20] concerns the delamination between 0-degree layers, and the arrest toughness, G_{arr} , in this work is not for a pure Mode II delamination and is the toughness at the 0/90 interface. Further more, similar scatter in the measurement of arrest toughness and the coincidence between the arrest and initiation energies for Mode II delamination has been reported in [21] for Glass/Epoxy composite.

4. CONCLUSION

The Carbon/PEEK composite exhibits the same impact damage mechanisms as epoxy composites. Thermal residual stresses have significant effects on transverse matrix

cracks and must be included in damage prediction. The impact induced delamination occurs under a displacement controlled condition. The strain energy release rate at delamination arrest seems to be a reasonably good candidate for predicting the size of delamination in laminated composites under impact.

6. REFERENCE

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